

FCT RESEARCH AND INNOVATION LANDSCAPE COUNTRY PROFILE: BELGIUM

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About ENACT

ENACT is a knowledge network focused on the fight against crime and terrorism (FCT). The network is funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme in Cluster 3 – Civil Security for Society. The project addresses the call topic HORIZON-CL3-2022-SSRI-01-02 ‘Knowledge Networks for Security Research & Innovation’, aiming to collect, aggregate, process, disseminate and make the most of the existing knowledge in the FCT area.

The project aims to satisfy two major ambitions,

- Provide evidence-based support to the decision-makers in the EU research and innovation (R&I) ecosystem in the FCT domain, targeted explicitly at enabling more effective and efficient programming of EU-funded R&I for the fight against crime and terrorism.
- Act as a catalyst for the uptake of innovation by enhancing the visibility and reliability of innovative FCT security solutions.

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Overview

The **Fight against Crime and Terrorism (FCT)** domain is a critical pillar within the European Union's security research framework, designed to address the increasingly complex and transnational threats facing Europe today. **FCT** research aims to provide innovative solutions, tools, and knowledge to empower law enforcement, policymakers, and civil society to prevent, detect, and respond to criminal and terrorist activities across the continent. The European Union supports collaborative research and innovation through key programmes like **Horizon Europe**, focusing on multidisciplinary approaches that combine advanced technology with robust legal, ethical, and societal safeguards.

In line with **ENACT's** objectives, this flash report is part of a series of reports that reviews the **FCT R&I** ecosystem in each EU Member State based on their participation in EU-funded **Security Research** under the **FCT** area between 2021 and 2024. The data used for the report comes from the most recent data available from **CORDIS** and the **Horizon Dashboard**, combined with data processed by **ENACT** under its **Structured Knowledge Base (SKB)**.

Belgium Infobox

Capital: Brussels

Official EU Language(s): Dutch, French, German

EU Member State: since 1 January 1958

Currency: euro (€)

Euro Area Member: since 1 January 1999

Schengen Area Member: since 26 March 1995

Figures

- **Geographical size:** 30 667km²
- **Population:** 11 900 123 (2025)

The section above provides institutional, territorial and demographic information situating Belgium within the EU.¹ Belgium's position as a centrally connected Member State, with strategic maritime access, shapes both its participation in EU internal-security cooperation and its exposure to **Transnational Crime** dynamics. As the geographical and political centre of the EU, Belgium occupies a key position for cross-border illicit practices.

To contextualise how these structural characteristics translate into concrete crime dynamics, analytical assessments such as the Global Organised Crime Index (OCINDEX)² examine the main illicit markets, the types of actors involved and the institutional responses addressing these threats. According to the OCINDEX, Belgium is identified as an entry point to diverse forms of **Trafficking. Drug Trafficking**, especially cocaine via the port of Antwerp, continues to represent a high part of the country's criminal market. Belgium continues to be a central hub for **Human Smuggling and Trafficking**. Increasing numbers related to the **Illicit Trade of Counterfeit Goods** also showcase the importance of international and national cooperation for crime prevention and repression of crime. Belgium has also faced an increase in **Cybercrime**, which is often also transnational.

¹ https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/eu-countries/belgium_en

² https://ocindex.net/assets/downloads/2025/english/ocindex_profile_belgium_2025.pdf

Belgian resilience is characterised by strong international cooperation and **Victim and Witness Support**, with increasing political leadership and governance. Belgium's resilience score had a slight increase from 2024 to 2025, putting the country in the 25th position worldwide. However, the Belgian resilience score is the second worst one from the 11 Western European countries.

R&I in the **FCT** domain in the country aligns with broader EU values and goals, with a large focus on national and international collaboration and **Information and Intelligence Sharing**. Research projects count on participation from actors from different sectors, including **Law Enforcement Authorities** and higher education entities, allowing for creative solutions for the **FCT** challenges.

Country overview in FCT Research & Innovation

Belgium's country profile in the **FCT** domain will be examined from three perspectives: policy coverage, functional coverage, and technology, in accordance with the **EU Civil Security Taxonomy (EUCST)**.³

FCT Policy Coverage

Figure 1 below illustrates the policy coverage of Belgium participation, categorised into the main **Security Research** areas: **OC (Organised Crime)**, **TR (Terrorism and Radicalisation)**, **CC (Cybercrime)**, and **HSI (Other Horizontal Societal Issues)**. Figure 2 further disaggregates this engagement by showing the distribution across the relevant policy sub-areas within each theme. This distribution is based on the participation of Belgian entities in **FCT** topics, as well as their perceived areas of expertise identified through fairs and conferences.

Overall, Belgium's participation in the **FCT** research landscape shows a diversified thematic distribution across the policy domains defined in the **EUCST**. Belgian involvement is mostly represented in **CC**, followed by an almost equal distribution among the **HSI**, **OC**, and **TR** topics.

Figure 1: Policy coverage across Belgian participants in the ENACT Stakeholders Directory

³ https://home-affairs.ec.europa.eu/networks/ceris-community-european-research-and-innovation-security/eu-security-market-study/eu-civil-security-taxonomy-and-taxonomy-explorer_en

Within the **CC** domain, the largest share of Belgium participation is concentrated in projects focusing on a range of issues related to technologically enabled crime. The majority of projects address issues related to the **Darknet**, including **Illegal Markets** and **Cryptocurrencies**, showing a connection to the current state of the criminal market in the country. A current trend in the projects is also research on combating **Child Sexual Abuse** and the best practices in **Digital Forensics**, relating to recent concerns in the region. Projects related to **Attacks Against Information Systems** represent the smallest part of projects with Belgian participation, even though there is an increasing number of these types of attacks, and there are new policies in related matters.

The **HSI** domain represents the second most addressed area of Belgian participation. Almost a third of the projects with Belgian participation in the **HSI** domain address **Disinformation and Fake News**. Different societal security themes are also addressed in projects with Belgian entities, including **Domestic Violence and Sexual Abuse**, **Youth Criminality**, and **Hate Speech**. Nevertheless, none of the projects tackles **Travel Intelligence (PNR)**.

Within the **OC** domain, Belgian participation is primarily focused on the **Trafficking of Humans and Goods**, which emerges as the most prominent topic. This focus is directly connected with the country’s profile and the priorities established in the EU and in Belgium. Significant activity is also observed in **Economic Crime, Corruption and Fraud**. This profile indicates a focus on transnational and economically driven criminal activities.

The **TR** domain is also well represented, with Belgian contributions addressing **Radicalisation** and the **Protection of Public Spaces** as key areas. These activities reflect a focus on prevention, resilience, and the protection of public environments.

Figure 2: Policy coverage at level 3 across Belgian stakeholders

FCT Functions Coverage

Figure 3 presents Belgium’s functional profile within the **FCT** research ecosystem, which demonstrates a strong concentration in **Intelligence and Data Management**, complemented by **Training and Investigative Capabilities**. The distribution of functional activities reflects a profile oriented towards national and international operational support to **Law Enforcement** and data-driven investigation.

The most prominent functional area is **Data, Information and Intelligence Gathering, Management, and Exploitation**. This domain is closely followed by **Investigation and Forensics**, and **Training and Exercises**. The chart showcases the Belgian and EU’s focus on capacitation to allow for effective investigation, including in digital crimes. Projects with Belgian participation evaluate and explore data potential while recognising the importance of national and international cooperation.

Other various functions are also tackled by projects with Belgian entities. As complementary to the main topics, **Information, Communication and Data Security** are also topics addressed by **R&I** initiatives, alongside the **Detection of Goods, Substances, Assets, People and Incidents**.

Figure 3: Functions coverage across Belgian stakeholders

FCT Technology Domain Coverage

As can be observed in Figure 4, the technological profile of Belgium's contributions is closely aligned with its functional strengths in investigation, forensics, and intelligence exploitation. However, in another movement, the most addressed type of technology is **General Equipment**. Nevertheless, the following most addressed topics, **Internet-Based Investigation** and **Data Analytics**, reconfirm the country's position and focus in developing and analysing **Digital Forensics**, combating **Cybercrime**, and data-driven investigations.

Other prominent topics are **Training and Simulation**, **Communications and Interoperability**. Both themes are somehow connected and complementary to the topics related to **Internet-Based Investigation** and **Data Analytics**. Training becomes essential to following new developments and technologies, such as in **Internet-Based Investigation**, as well as for simulating new technologies before deployment. Also, **Communications and Interoperability** and infrastructure development are crucial to supporting the technologies being developed and deployed.

Belgium still has significant participation in the majority of technology topics, including **Monitoring Tools and Services**, **Data Storage and Exchange**, and **Safety Equipment**. However, there is minimal or no involvement of Belgian entities in projects related to **Search Devices and Tools**, **Laboratory Equipment for Gathering and Forensic Analysis of Samples**, and **Facilitation Systems and Secure Databases**. While data security should go hand-in-hand with data-driven solutions, the topic might not be the central issue of the mapped projects or could be more broadly addressed in other calls.

This distribution reflects a broader specialisation in cyber-enabled security technologies and intelligence-driven approaches, aligning with both national capabilities and evolving European security priorities.

Figure 4: Technology coverage across Belgian stakeholders

Overview of Belgium's Horizon Europe participation metrics

The next figure compares Belgium's and the EU's key performance indicators in the **Horizon Europe FCT** domain, highlighting Belgium's strong engagement and specific contributions relative to the European reference figures.

Belgium	23	1.70	€ 430,295.88	€ 422,257.83	10	€ 2,079,133.91
	Signed Grants	Average Participation	Average Total Cost	Average EU Contribution	SME Participation	SME Net EU Contribution
EU	41	18.12	€ 4,310,115.27	€ 3,987,660.71	172	€ 44,114,024.00
	Signed Grants	Average Participation	Average Total Cost	Average EU Contribution	SME Participation	SME Net EU Contribution

Figure 5: Belgian project participation metrics compared to the EU

In this period, more than half (23 out of 41) of the signed **FCT** grants included Belgium beneficiaries, representing a sizable portion of EU activity in this domain. Belgian participation in **FCT** projects has reinforced the country's position as a leading research hub, including through different projects having more than one Belgian partner. This scenario confirms the country's continuous collaboration between both Belgian entities and international entities, marked by a well-coordinated research system.

Belgium is positioned as one of the leading countries in **FCT** projects. On average, Belgian entities represent 19% of participants in **FCT** grants (39 from the 743 total). In other words, on average, an **FCT** grant has 18.12 beneficiaries, out of which 1.70 are Belgian. With respect to SME participation, Belgian SMEs represent only an 5,8% of the total number of SMEs involved in **FCT** grants under the Horizon Programme. However, SMEs represent around 25% of the Belgian entities involved in **FCT** projects, which is comparable with other leading countries such as Spain and Germany.

Regardless of the country's small size, Belgium's participation in **FCT** projects demonstrates the central role national entities have occupied in EU research, involving both academic and industrial actors. Also, Belgian participants received almost 6% of all net EU contributions, which places Belgium as the sixth country with the highest net contribution.

These numbers can be justified both by the relevant involvement in project activities, especially with high-level expertise developed by higher education entities, and by the higher personnel costs faced by the country. Despite these high costs, Belgium's ability to secure a high number of projects highlights its competitiveness and its capacity to position itself as a relevant and reliable partner within European security research consortia.

Based on the indicators presented in Figure 5 and the country comparison data in Table 1, Belgium ranks seventh in terms of total participations.

Country Code	Country	Signed Grants	Total Participations by Country	Net EU Contribution
EL	Greece	34	90	€ 26,290,653.24
ES	Spain	34	87	€ 17,409,733.00
IT	Italy	25	65	€ 17,590,799.90
UK	United Kingdom	30	52	€ 4,525,528.75
DE	Germany	27	48	€ 13,558,133.33
FR	France	21	43	€ 10,163,819.63
BE	Belgium	23	39	€ 9,606,930.16
FI	Finland	22	29	€ 5,954,334.86
PT	Portugal	21	28	€ 4,924,522.00
NL	Netherlands	19	27	€ 8,513,248.75
PL	Poland	16	26	€ 5,898,789.00
CY	Cyprus	18	23	€ 5,723,581.25
RO	Romania	14	22	€ 2,733,978.00
MD	Moldova	18	20	€ 1,288,120.00
AT	Austria	12	16	€ 4,347,636.75
BG	Bulgaria	6	13	€ 2,241,263.14
CZ	Czechia	10	13	€ 2,061,742.25
LU	Luxembourg	10	11	€ 4,401,443.75
IE	Ireland	7	10	€ 3,456,761.80
SE	Sweden	10	10	€ 2,128,071.25
EE	Estonia	7	9	€ 1,177,348.75
SI	Slovenia	4	8	€ 1,201,050.00
IL	Israel	4	5	€ 1,761,025.00
RS	Serbia	4	5	€ 478,496.25
HU	Hungary	3	4	€ 1,731,153.75
HR	Croatia	2	3	€ 602,395.26
LT	Lithuania	2	3	€ 420,080.00
MT	Malta	3	3	€ 283,356.00
NO	Norway	3	3	€ 1,071,048.75
SK	Slovakia	1	3	€ 831,038.50
CA	Canada	2	2	€ 418,417.50
DK	Denmark	2	2	€ 107,375.00
XK	Kosovo*	2	2	€ 78,750.00
MK	North Macedonia	2	2	€ 67,226.25
TR	Türkiye	1	2	€ 160,432.50
AL	Albania	1	1	€ 48,750.00
BA	Bosnia and Herzegovina	1	1	€ 59,625.00
IS	Iceland	1	1	€ 42,430.00
UA	Ukraine	1	1	€ 135,000.00
CH	Switzerland	8	11	€ 0.00

Table 1: Comparison of Belgium to other participating countries in Horizon Europe for signed grants, total project participations and net EU contribution

*This designation is without prejudice to positions on status and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on Kosovo's declaration of independence.

Participants Summary

Belgian participation in **Horizon Europe CL3-FCT** projects encompasses a broad range of organisations, including research centres, universities, industry, and public sector bodies. The involvement of both well-established institutions and emerging players signals a robust and healthy ecosystem. The figure below compares Belgium with the full EU ecosystem.

Figure 6: Organisational types of Belgian participation compared to the EU average in Horizon Europe projects

Particularly significant is the active role played by **Higher or Secondary Education Establishments** reflecting scientific excellence and bringing research into action in project designs, which is made possible also by the high number of industry representatives involved in FCT grants. There is also a high level of participation of **Other** entities, representing 21% of all Belgian organisations, which includes a significant number of non-profit organisations based in the country.

When analysing individual participants by their type, the following overview highlights the current key organisations involved.

Top End Users

End User	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Police Federale Belge	€ 371,875.00	2	€ 371,875.00
Zone de Police Bruxelles Ixelles	€ 201,125.00	1	€ 201,125.00
Politiezone: Eeklo - Kaprijke - Sint-Laureins	€ 69,720.00	1	€ 69,720.00
Politiezone: Boom - Hemiksem - Niel - Rumst - Schelle	€ 36,250.00	1	€ 36,250.00
Ville de Liege	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Grand Total	€ 678,970	6	€ 678,970

Top Research and Technology Organisations

Research and Technology Organisation	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Creative Workers-Creatieve Werkers VZW	€216,250.00	1	€216,250.00
Nationaal Instituut Voor Criminalistiek en Criminologie - Institut National de Criminalistique et de Criminologie	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Grand Total	€ 216,250	2	€ 216,250

Top Industry

Industrial Organisation	Total Cost	Signed Grants	Total EU Contribution
Zabala Brussels	€ 417,500.00	1	€ 397,250.00
Timelex	€ 408,297.50	2	€ 408,297.50
Squaredev	€ 407,500.00	1	€ 285,250.00
Voxdale	€ 204,375.00	1	€ 204,375.00
European Organisation for Security	€ 180,000.00	1	€ 180,000.00
Vlaamse Maatschappij voor Watervoorziening	€ 141,250.00	1	€ 98,875.00
Evenflow	€ 104,023.91	1	€ 104,023.91
Nokia Bell	€ 0.00	1	€ 0.00
Grand Total	€ 1,862,946	9	€ 1,678,071

Top Academia

Higher Education	Total Cost	Signed Grants	EU Contribution
Vrije Universiteit Brussel	€ 2,614,231.25	8	€ 2,614,231.25
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	€ 2,326,826.25	4	€ 2,326,826.25
Universiteit Gent	€ 436,875.00	1	€ 436,875.00
Universite Catholique de Louvain	€ 389,500.00	1	€ 389,500.00
Grand Total	€ 5,767,433	14	€ 5,767,433

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Horizon Europe FCT Proposals Summary

Figure 7 presents a comparative overview of Belgium’s and the EU’s performance in **Horizon Europe FCT** proposal activities, allowing for a direct analysis of Belgium's contribution and competitiveness.

Belgium’s participation is characterised by a moderate volume of submitted proposals. Belgian organisations were involved in a total of 175 eligible proposals, representing a comparable but still smaller share of overall submissions to other leading countries, such as France (131), Italy (162) and Greece (200).

Belgium	119	23	175	€ 44,176,603.88	19%
	Eligible Proposals	Retained Proposals	Eligible Applications	Eligible EU Contribution	Success Rate
EU	278	39	4458	€ 1,099,171,410.00	14%
	Eligible Proposals	Retained Proposals	Eligible Applications	Eligible EU Contribution	Success Rate

Figure 7: Statistics for Horizon Europe proposal submission for Belgium compared to the EU overall

In this period, 23 out of 39 retained **FCT** proposals include Belgian beneficiaries, representing a sizable portion of EU activity in this domain. Belgium’s success rate of 19% is above the EU’s average of 14%. The country’s involvement in **FCT** projects is marked by a large participation of higher education entities with a tradition of research development, representing 36% of the total Belgian entities participating in **FCT** projects.

Belgian entities were involved in a small share of the total eligible applications, around 4%, which can indicate a focused yet consistent level of engagement in proposals. From the 175 eligible applications, 119 were eligible proposals, showcasing the country’s alignment with call priorities and strategic research initiatives.

Horizon Europe FCT Projects Summary

Belgian entities are involved in a large number of projects, with Belgium consistently engaging as a relevant partner in a wide range of initiatives. Around half of the projects with Belgian participation have more than one Belgian entity involved, showcasing how the country's entities are involved in core different tasks, from legal and ethical analysis to technical development.

Acronym	Project Title	Type	No.
2PS	2PS - Prevent & Protect Through Support	RIA	1
GANNDALF	A Ground-breaking collaboration framework realizing the next era of cybercrime Detection And multi-stakeholder investigation For LEAs, judicial ecosystems, and citizens.	RIA	1
VANGUARD	advanced technological solutions coupled with societal-oriented Understanding and Awareness for Disrupting trafficking in human beings	IA	1
GATHERINGS	COMMON STANDARDS FOR SECURITY, PRIVACY AND COST OF THE SURVEILLANCE OF PUBLIC GATHERINGS	CSA	1
EMERITUS	Environmental crimes' intelligence and investigation protocol based on multiple data sources	IA	1
EITHOS	European Identity Theft Observatory System	RIA	2
FERMI	Fake News Risk Mitigator	IA	4
GEMS	Gaming Ecosystem as a Multilayered Security Threat	RIA	1
KOBAN	Identifying future capabilities for Community Policing	RIA	2
LAGO	Lessen Data Access and Governance Obstacles	IA	2
POLIICE	Powerful Lawful Interception, Investigation, and Intelligence	RIA	1
PRESERVE	Protecting European public spaces against Emergent hostile drone threats through an advanced multidimensional shield and cross-border intelligence	RIA	1
PERIVALLON	Protecting the European territory from organised environmental crime through intelligent threat detection tools	IA	1
SENSOR	Reliable biometric technologies to assist Police authorities in combating terrorism and organized crime	IA	1
RITHMS	Research, Intelligence and Technology for Heritage and Market Security	RIA	1
SAFE-CITIES	risk-based Approach For the protection of public spaces in European CITIES	IA	1
OSPREY	Online Safety and Security for Protection of Public-Facing Professionals and Democratic Resilience	RIA	2

Acronym	Project Title	Type	No.
AMALTHEA	EnAbling a Model-driven deep understAnding of the roLe of gender Towards a Holistic solution against Extremism and radicalization Activities	RIA	2
SALUS	Strengthening law enforcement with advanced IoT forensic tools and enriched investigation schemes, realised by a Software Defined Network Security-as-a-Service architecture	RIA	1
CapCell	Innovative forensic trace investigation via microfluidics and single-cell genomics	RIA	2
SALVUS	SALVUS (Ensuring SAfer justice outcomes in onLine, including undercoVer, child sexUal abuse inveStigations)	RIA	3
ECLIPSE	PrEventing and Combating onLine and offline hate speech and dIsinformation through multidisciPlinary innovation, education, and awareNeSs in Europe	IA	4
BEHOLDER	Build and Extend CBRN-E related Hazard-Assessment and Anomaly Detection Capabilities on Urban Environment.	IA	2

This level of engagement demonstrates Belgium’s capacity to actively contribute to cross-border **R&D** activities and to position itself as a reliable and competitive partner within **Horizon Europe** projects, leveraging its research ecosystem.

The following section presents a series of charts detailing the policy, functional, and technological coverage of the projects, based on the comprehensive list of projects outlined above.

Figure 8: Policy project coverage according to projects with Belgian participation

Figure 9: L3 Policy coverage according to projects with Belgian participation

Figure 10: Functions coverage according to projects with Belgian participation

Figure 11: Technology coverage according to projects with Belgian participation

Final Remarks

Belgium's participation in the FCT research ecosystem under **Horizon Europe** demonstrates a competitive and well-positioned profile, characterised by above-average proposal performance, consistent project involvement, and specialised expertise in key security domains. The country's established and growing research ecosystem allows national entities to collaborate effectively with each other, as well as with international partners, securing a significant number of projects.

From a policy perspective, Belgium's involvement in FCT projects covers all FCT domains, with a clear emphasis on **Cybercrime**, complemented by balanced engagement in **Organised Crime**, particularly **Trafficking of Humans and Goods**, and relevant contributions to **Human and Societal Issues** and **Terrorism and Radicalisation**. This distribution, marked by a focus on digital domains, reflects both European and national priorities and expertise, positioning Belgium as a contributor to a wide range of security challenges. In terms of functional capabilities, Belgian participation is strongly oriented towards **Data and Intelligence Management**, and **Investigation and Forensics**, supported by **Training and Exercises**. Belgium's functional profile highlights the country's focus on data- and intelligence-driven investigations, which requires ongoing literacy and personnel training to develop the skills needed to explore the full potential of information.

Technologically, Belgium maintains a strong focus on **General Equipment**, showcasing the continued importance of these assets for the **FCT** domain. Nevertheless, aligned with EU priorities, Belgian participation has an increased focus on **Internet-Based Investigation** and **Data Analytics**. These complement **General Equipment**, allowing for better alignment with the digitalisation of security threats and the growing importance of information-centric approaches to **Law Enforcement**.

Belgium's participation in **FCT** grants is characterised by a strong academic profile, with significant involvement of **Higher Education Entities**. Industrial and private actors also represent a relevant percentage of the Belgian entities involved in **FCT** grants, showcasing the goal of bringing research into practice and to the market. This combination of academic and industry profiles is well aligned with the EU ecosystem and goals of market development, which could be enhanced by greater SME participation.

Overall, Belgium continues to be a central hub for research initiatives, with relevant actors involved in different themes within the **FCT** domain. Belgian entities are well prepared to participate in international consortia, with experience in both national and transnational collaboration. Expertise ranging from digital areas to conventional or general forensics allows Belgian entities to deliver and participate in diverse contributions within the **Horizon Europe** programme.

For more information and guidance regarding Belgium participation in **Horizon Europe Cluster 3** and potential collaboration opportunities, stakeholders are encouraged to consult the National Contact Points (NCPs) available through the Horizon Europe NCP Portal: <https://horizoneuropencportal.eu/>, where dedicated Belgium NCPs can provide support on funding opportunities, partner search, and proposal development.

A note on data sources

The data used to compile this report is from the following sources

- **ENACT Stakeholder Directory**, where relevant organisations participating in **Horizon Europe**, **Horizon 2020** or relevant security events have been compiled and categorised according to the **EU Civil Security Market Taxonomy** for policy levels two and three, functions and technology.
- **ENACT Project Directory**, where relevant projects have been compiled and categorised according to the **EU Civil Security Market Taxonomy** for policy levels two and three, functions and technology.
- The **Horizon Dashboard** for R&I Projects and R&I Proposals.⁴

An explorable version of the **ENACT Stakeholders Directory** is available on the **ENACT** website.⁵

⁴Horizon Dashboard - <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-dashboard>

⁵ENACT Stakeholders Map - <https://enact-eu.net/enact-fct-stakeholder-map/>

ENACT.

European Network Against
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